

Third Update to Scientific Applications of Uncrewed Vehicles in Svalbard (UAV Svalbard 4)

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Update of [chapter 3 in SESS report 2020](#), [chapter 5 in SESS report 2021](#), and [chapter 6 in SESS report 2022](#)

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1. Introduction

This chapter presents the second update to the report on the scientific applications of unmanned vehicles in Svalbard, originally published in the 2020 State of Environmental Science in Svalbard (SESS) Report (Hann et al. 2021) and first updated in the 2021 edition (Hann et al. 2022). The initial contribution provided the first systematic review of research in Svalbard using aerial, surface, and underwater unmanned platforms, while the 2021 update added 15 new publications and summarised the transition to the new European drone regulations. A further step was taken in 2022, when a set of practical guidelines for UAV research in Svalbard was proposed (Hann et al. 2023), with a focus on data standards, fieldwork planning, and community best practices. This chapter follows in the footsteps of these previous communications and introduces a total of 50 new publications, including all work published through August 2025.

Drone abbreviations

UAV – Uncrewed or Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
 UAS – Uncrewed or Unmanned Aircraft System
 RPAS – Remotely Piloted Aircraft System
 USV – Uncrewed or Unmanned Surface Vehicle
 ASV – Autonomous Surface Vehicle
 ROV – Remotely Operated Vehicle
 AUV – Autonomous Underwater Vehicle

Since the first UAV Svalbard chapter in 2020, measurable progress has been made on several of the original recommendations, while others remain pending. The 2021 and 2022 updates strengthened the community focus on metadata, standards, and best practices, and initiated efforts for broader data sharing. However, some recommendations—such as shared platforms or improved regulatory frameworks—are still at an early stage. Table 1 provides a short overview of the developments.

Table 1: Overview of previous recommendations and their implementation status.

Recommendation	Status 2025	Efforts made
Framework for UAV activity planning (SESS report 2022)	Implemented	Information included in SESS report 2022 and shared in community
Disseminate information about new EU regulations (SESS report 2021)	Implemented	Information included in SESS report 2022 and shared in community
Standardisation of UAV operations, data processing, and data dissemination procedures (SESS report 2020)	Ongoing	Guidelines for UAV fieldwork and metadata published in SESS report 2022
Data storage and data accessibility (SESS report 2020, SESS report 2022)	Ongoing	Updated UAV database in this report; implementation with partner databases (e.g. DataVerse) discussed
Education, experience transfer, knowledge base, and training (SESS report 2020, SESS report 2022)	Ongoing	Guidelines for UAV fieldwork and metadata published in SESS report 2022; UAV4Svalbard training course ¹ by SIOS in 2023
Establish an interdisciplinary communication platform (SESS report 2021, SESS report 2022)	Ongoing	Discussions during SIOS events; No major event (e.g. conference) established
Extend infrastructure and access to advanced systems (SESS report 2020, SESS report 2022)	Limited	Some ad hoc sharing mostly by researchers at UNIS; no large UAV platforms
Lower barriers for operations in Svalbard (SESS report 2022)	Limited	Individual projects apply for exemptions; new barriers have emerged
Develop National Standard Scenarios for Svalbard (NSTS) (SESS report 2021)	Not implemented	NSTS system has been discontinued; no longer applicable

¹ <https://sios-svalbard.org/UAV4Svalbard>

The motivation for this update is fourfold. First, to generate an up-to-date overview of drone research conducted in Svalbard. Second, to provide a resource that can facilitate the re-use of existing datasets in new scientific studies. Third, to highlight technological developments that have shaped the field in recent years. And fourth, to identify

emerging trends and potentials in the application of uncrewed systems for environmental science in Svalbard. In addition, this chapter provides an update on the regulations governing drone usage in Svalbard, along with recommendations for how SIOS can further support and strengthen the use of drones in future research.

2. Methods

The literature review for this update follows the same approach as in the previous reports. Relevant publications were identified through systematic searches in Scopus² and Google Scholar³, using a combination of keywords referring both to uncrewed vehicle technologies and to the Svalbard region. Search terms for the platforms included the keywords “drone”, “UAV”, “UAS”, “RPAS”, “USV”, “ASV”, “ROV”, and “AUV”. These were combined with geographic keywords “Svalbard”, “Spitzbergen”, and “Spitsbergen”. The search was carried out on 18 August 2025 and included only published articles,

papers, and reports – it did not include databases.

The resulting publications were screened to exclude unrelated studies and duplicates. All remaining entries were categorised according to vehicle type, research discipline, study area, and main product type, in line with the database structure used in the original UAV Svalbard SESS report (Hann et al. 2021). This ensures consistency across the different updates and allows for long-term tracking of trends in uncrewed vehicle applications in Svalbard.

3. Database update

The updated literature review has been implemented in the searchable online database⁴ and has also been published (Hann 2025). It now contains a total of 115 entries, of which 50 have been added since the previous update. Each entry corresponds to a publication that applies uncrewed aerial, surface, or underwater systems in Svalbard. As in the previous reports, the database records key characteristics for each study, including discipline, type of vehicle, sensor payload, study area, and product type. This structure allows for a consistent overview of the development of uncrewed vehicle applications in Svalbard and makes it possible to track disciplinary trends, technological advances, and emerging hotspots of research activity over time.

The number of publications using drones in Svalbard has steadily increased since the first paper in 2007 (Figure 1). While early activity was limited, the field has expanded rapidly in the past decade, peaking in 2021 with 18 publications. This peak is likely related to the COVID-19 pandemic, which provided researchers with additional time to process and publish existing datasets. Publication numbers appear lower in 2023 to 2025, but this is partly explained by a backlog of unpublished datasets and by the fact that the 2025 count only includes work published up to August. Overall, the long-term trend underlines the growing importance of drone systems in Arctic research.

² <https://elsevier.com/products/scopus>

³ <https://scholar.google.com/>

⁴ https://sios-svalbard.org/UAV_Svalbard

Figure 1: Number of publications using uncrewed vehicles in Svalbard (2007–2025)

Drone vehicles are applied across a wide range of scientific disciplines in Svalbard (Figure 2). They are used most often in geology, ecology, and glaciology, each with a substantial number of studies. Geomorphology, oceanography, and atmospheric research also make frequent use of drone-based methods, while fields such as technology development, snow, sea ice, and cultural preservation remain less represented. This distribution highlights both the broad relevance of uncrewed systems and the key domains where they have become especially well established as research tools.

Figure 2: Number of publications by scientific discipline using uncrewed vehicles in Svalbard

Most studies based on drones in Svalbard are conducted during summer (Figure 3), reflecting the logistical ease of access and favourable weather conditions. Considerably fewer publications report fieldwork in spring, autumn, or winter, highlighting the seasonal bias of current drone-based research during the periods when light is available. This highlights that there may be a lack of datasets for the dark season.

Figure 3: Seasonal distribution of publications using uncrewed vehicles in Svalbard

The application of drones in Svalbard has increased steadily since 2007, with UAVs clearly dominating throughout the entire period (Figure 4). UAVs account for the vast majority of publications and have become the standard tool for research across many disciplines, particularly geology, ecology, and glaciology. Other platforms, including AUVs, ROVs, ASVs, and USVs, are used to a much smaller extent, though their contribution has grown slightly

in recent years. These systems are mainly applied in oceanography and marine sciences, reflecting the potential of autonomous underwater and surface technologies in polar research. Together, these trends highlight the potential to better integrate different uncrewed technologies within the observational pyramid to achieve multi-scale, cross-domain perspectives in Svalbard research.

Figure 4: Number of publications by vehicle type in Svalbard (2007–2025)

4. Updates to regulations

Since the last SESS chapter on drones in 2021, new regulations have come into force that directly affect the use of drones in Svalbard. Most notably, the use of drones in protected areas (including national parks and nature reserves) is now prohibited under the framework of the Svalbard Environmental Protection Act (Svalbardmiljøloven; LOV-2001-06-15-79) and the associated conservation regulations. This applies to both aerial and marine platforms. As stated by the Governor of Svalbard: “Drones are prohibited in all protected areas in Svalbard” (Syssemesteren, 2025). The restriction is intended to reduce disturbance to wildlife and safeguard vulnerable environments.

In addition, amendments to the Svalbard Environmental Protection Act entered into force on 1 January 2025 and introduced new provisions concerning bird protection (Regjeringen, 2024). Between 1 April and 31 August, drone flights are not permitted within 500 metres of bird cliffs in order to avoid disturbance during the breeding season. These provisions further tighten the regulatory framework for scientific drone operations in Svalbard, even outside of protected areas, especially during the summer months when most fieldwork is carried out. In summary, the following rules currently apply in addition to the EU regulations (Syssemesteren, 2025):

- Flying drones is prohibited in all protected areas (national parks, nature reserves, etc.).
- Drones must stay at least 500 m away from bird cliffs between 1 April and 31 August to avoid disturbing nesting birds.
- Drones may not fly within 5 km of airports (e.g. Longyearbyen, Ny-Ålesund), unless permission has been granted.
- A radio silence zone in practice prohibits drone use within a 20 km radius around Ny-Ålesund. The 2-32 GHz frequency band is exclusively licensed to the Norwegian Mapping Authority. Most drones use this frequency band for telemetry.
- All drone operations must avoid disturbance to wildlife and people, avoid damage to nature or cultural heritage, and comply with both aviation and environmental protection laws.

These restrictions significantly limit the use of both aerial and marine platforms for research. Special permissions can be granted by the Governor of Svalbard, but the application process is restrictive and often challenging for projects with short lead times. Currently, applications for exception must be filed via the Research in Svalbard⁵ platform.

In addition to the Svalbard-specific rules, the EU regulatory framework for aerial drones has also evolved since 2021. The most important change concerns the Open category, which from 1 January 2024 requires new UAVs to carry a CE class identification label (C0–C4) in accordance with Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945. Drones purchased before this date without class labels (“legacy drones”) may still be operated, but those weighing between 250 grams and 25 kilograms may only be operated far away from uninvolved persons (subcategory A3). Legacy drones weighing less than 250 grams may still be operated in subcategory A1. (For details on the subcategories, see Appendix 3 in Hann et al. 2022.). The Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 also clarifies requirements for remote pilot training and certification, and most drones in the Open category must now be equipped with a remote identification system to ensure traceability of operations. These provisions, are applicable across all EASA⁶ member states and are set out in Regulation (EU) 2019/947 and its subsequent amendments (EASA, 2024).

5. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

Drones have become an important cross-disciplinary tool in Svalbard research. Since our first review (Hann et al. 2021), their use has expanded beyond geomorphology, glaciology, and ecology into disciplines such as oceanography, atmospheric sciences, and cultural heritage. This underlines their role as a versatile platform that connects different scientific fields.

A key advancement since the last update is the integration of drones into the observational pyramid. The combination of aerial and marine drones provides measurements at scales between satellites, normal-altitude aerial photographs, and in situ instruments, enabling upscaling and

downscaling across domains. In this way, drones contribute directly to strengthening the SIOS observing system.

Future potential lies in further combining drone-based methods across disciplines—for example, linking ecological surveys with UAV mapping or coupling atmospheric profiling with marine campaigns. A concrete illustration comes from an Arctic Field Grant project in 2024, where researchers from the UAV Lab and the Applied Underwater Robotic (AUR) Lab at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) conducted joint fieldwork at Fridtjovbreen. In this campaign, ROVs were used to map the subsurface

⁵ <https://www.researchinsvalbard.no>

⁶ European Union Aviation Safety Agency. Member states: AT, BE, BG, HR, CY, CZ, DK, EE, FI, FR, DE, GR, HU, IE, IT, LV, LT, LU, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SK, SI, ES, SE, IS, LI, NO, CH

glacier terminus while UAVs simultaneously surveyed the ice front from the air. This combined data will be used to characterise the dynamics of the glacier terminus system in greater detail. Together with satellite imagery, this creates a multi-

scale dataset that demonstrates how drones can anchor the observational pyramid in practice and strengthen the integration of the SIOS observing system.

6. Recommendations for the future

The rapid growth of drone-based research in Svalbard highlights both new opportunities and emerging challenges. To strengthen the role of drones within the SIOS observing system, we propose the following recommendations to be facilitated by SIOS.

- **Shared drone data repository**

SIOS should establish a central repository for UAV, USV, and AUV datasets, with harmonised metadata standards and processing best-practices to ensure long-term storage, accessibility, and re-use across disciplines.

- **Shared platforms and sensor pool**

A coordinated pool of drone platforms, payloads, and real-time kinematic (RTK) positioning infrastructure hosted by SIOS or partner institutions would lower the entry barrier for groups without their own equipment and enable

broader participation in drone-based research.

- **Integration into the observational pyramid**

SIOS should actively support multi-platform campaigns that link in situ, drone, and satellite data, using drones as a bridging layer in the observational pyramid to strengthen cross-domain integration.

- **Training and competence building**

Targeted training in piloting, regulatory compliance, and data handling should be offered to researchers to ensure safe and efficient drone operations in Svalbard.

- **Dialogue with regulators and stakeholders**

SIOS should engage with the Governor of Svalbard (Sysselimesteren) and relevant stakeholders to reduce barriers for scientific drone use, ensuring that regulatory processes remain compatible with the needs of time-critical field campaigns.

7. Data availability

The literature database can be accessed via https://sios-svalbard.org/UAV_Svalbard and

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4293283>.

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9. References

- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 of 12 March 2019 on unmanned aircraft systems and on third-country operators of UAS. *Official Journal of the European Union*. https://data.europa.eu/eli/reg_del/2019/945/oj
- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 of 24 May 2019 on the rules and procedures for the operation of unmanned aircraft. *Official Journal of the European Union*. https://data.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2019/947/oj
- EASA (European Union Aviation Safety Agency) (2024) *Easy Access Rules for Unmanned Aircraft Systems*. Accessed August 2025. <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/document-library/easy-access-rules/easy-access-rules-unmanned-aircraft-systems-regulations-eu>
- Hann R (2025) SESS UAV Database - Database of Scientific Applications of Unmanned Vehicles in Svalbard. Version 2. Zenodo Dataset. <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4293283>
- Hann R, Altstädter B, Betlem P, Deja K, Dragańska-Deja K, Ewertowski M, Hartvich F, Jonassen M, Lampert A, Laska M, Sobota I, Stolvold R, Tomczyk A, Wojtysiak K, Zagórski P (2021) Scientific Applications of Unmanned Vehicles in Svalbard. SESS Report 2020, Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System. <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4293283>
- Hann R, Betlem P, Deja K, Hartvich F, Jonassen M, Lampert A, Laska M, Sobota I, Stolvold R, Zagórski P (2022) Update to Scientific Applications of Unmanned Vehicles in Svalbard. SESS Report 2021, Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System. <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5751959>
- Hann R, Betlem P, Deja K, Ewertowski M, Harm-Altstädter B, Jonassen M, Lampert A, Laska M, Sobota I, Stolvold R, Tomczyk A, Zagórski P (2023) Practical Guidelines for Scientific Application of Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles in Svalbard. SESS Report 2022, Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System. <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7371141>
- Regjeringen (2024) *Endringer i miljøregelverket på Svalbard*. Press release 23 February 2024. Accessed August 2025. <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/aktuelt/endringer-i-miljoregelverket-pa-svalbard/id3024960/>
- Svalbardmiljøloven; LOV-2001-06-15-79 (2001) *Lov 15 juni 2001 nr. 79 om miljøvern på Svalbard* (Svalbard Environmental Protection Act;). <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2001-06-15-79>
- Syssemesteren på Svalbard (2025) *Drones on Svalbard*. Press release, updated February 2025. Accessed August 2025. <https://www.syssemesteren.no/en/drones-on-svalbard/>

ALADINA UAV taking off from the airport in Ny-Ålesund. (Photo: Lutz Bretschneider)

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HIGHLIGHTS

Drone use in Svalbard science is expanding fast and spans many disciplines. New regulations restrict access, but drones remain vital in the observational pyramid. Shared data, recommended processing workflows, platforms, and dialogue with regulators are key for future research.

- **Researchers:** The complete catalogue of drone-related publications in Svalbard now has 115 entries, showing the future potential of the observational pyramid.
- **Pilots & project leaders:** New rules severely restrict drone operations in protected areas and near bird cliffs.
- **Regulators:** This overview shows where restrictions limit science and where dialogue can reduce barriers.

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This chapter provides an updated overview of drone-based research in Svalbard, building on 115 scientific articles published up to August 2025. The analysis shows that drones are now widely used across disciplines, with uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs) dominating but marine drone systems gradually gaining importance. Most studies are carried out in summer, leading to a seasonal bias in observations in the available datasets.

In 2021, new regulations under the *Svalbard Environmental Protection Act* introduced a general ban on drones in protected areas, and seasonal buffer zones around bird cliffs. These rules substantially constrain scientific operations, although exemptions can be granted by the Governor of Svalbard. In parallel, EU regulations have clarified requirements for class-marked drones, pilot training, and remote identification.

The broader implications of these new rules highlight both the challenges and opportunities of using drones in Arctic science. Drones are a

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Establish a shared SIOS drone data repository with common metadata standards.
- Create a pool of shared drone platforms and sensors.
- Support integration of drone data into the observational pyramid.
- Provide training in piloting, regulations, and data handling.
- Strengthen dialogue with the Governor of Svalbard and stakeholders to facilitate scientific drone use.

key element in the observational pyramid, linking satellites with in-situ data and enabling cross-disciplinary integration within the SIOS observing system. Their continued use is highly relevant for society, as they provide unique insights into climate change impacts, biodiversity, and environmental dynamics in Svalbard. To safeguard this potential, improved data sharing, access to shared platforms, competence building, and dialogue with regulators are urgently needed.

Aerial and underwater drones used to study Fridtjovbreen in a collaboration involving the NTNU UAV Lab and the NTNU Applied Underwater Robotic Lab. (Photo: Richard Hann)